

GENDER EQUALITY BECOMES SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDGs)

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Abstract: Gender equality is a growing issue along the times as society's views are increasingly open regarding the equal roles of men and women. In some countries, especially in the Middle East, South Asia, and Latin America, women cannot work for additional income without getting permission from their husbands or fathers. Gender equality and gender justice issues in Indonesia have existed for a long time. Gender is not a gender difference but a difference in social functions and roles formed by society towards women and men which results in the division of different social roles and functions. Currently, the Indonesian government is aggressively implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program, which is a sustainable program that is a non-binding global agreement that is universally applicable. Empowerment aims to make people able to do something independently without having to depend on others. The independence that exists as a result of empowerment in the form of economic independence, political independence, and others depends on the type of the existing program

Keywords: SDG's, Gender, Empowerment.

1. PREVALENCE OF GENDER EQUALITY

Gender equality is a growing issue along the times as society's views are increasingly open regarding the equal roles of men and women. The discussion of equality has become a global issue starting from the family level to the social life of the wider community. ILO (International Labor Organization) defines gender equality as equal rights, responsibilities, opportunities, treatment and assessment [1].

In some countries, especially in the Middle East, South Asia, and Latin America, women cannot work for additional income without getting permission from their husbands or fathers. Most women decide to work outside and played a double role as they have to be responsible for the household, child care, and providing food [2]. Women have a longer working hour compared to men. Gender pressure relations when the status of women changes results in increased family welfare. This is an important issue affecting the success or failure of development policies. Data from each country show that the salaries received by women are generally low, even at the lowest status. Thus, it can be seen that the position of women is vulnerable and not equal to that of men [3].

In a developing country like Indonesia, the gender equality issue is still a hot topic of discussion. Gender equality in Indonesia is still low among ASEAN countries based on the 2017 Gender Inequality Index (GII) ranks where Indonesia is ranked fourth. In ASEAN, Indonesia's Gender Development Index (GDI) is ranked 9th out of ten countries and is one of three ASEAN countries that are below the world average [4].

In 2019, Indonesia's Gender Development Index (GDI) increased with achievement of 91.07. This achievement exceeded the GDI achievement in 2015 which was 91.03 which had decreased significantly in 2016 to 90.82 [5]. However, since 2017, the GDI has continued to increase to date. Indonesia's IPD in 2019 increased by 0.55 points (0.08%) compared to 2018. The increase in GDI was due to the growth in the Human Development Index (HDI) for women which was higher than for men in 2018-2019 [6]. Although the GDI achievement in 2019 has restored the achievement in 2015, it has not succeeded in achieving the target of the Main Performance Indicators for the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection in 2019 which targets gender development of 92.00 [7].

2. HISTORY OF GENDER EQUALITY

Gender equality and gender justice issues in Indonesia have existed for a long time [8]. The pioneer of gender equality and gender justice is a female hero named RA Kartini in 1908. Gender equality and gender justice appeared due to gender injustice perpetrated by men against women so Kartini wanted to fight for realizing the equality between men and women [9]. Her goal in fighting for gender equality and gender justice is to equalize the position between men and women, especially in the field of education. She struggled for equal rights and positions between men and women starting from the field of education. She built a school for women as a form of fighting gender injustice and discrimination [9]. Women in Indonesia are still vulnerable to being victims of violence at this time as recorded in the National Commission on Violence against Women's 2018 Annual Records in which the number of reported violence cases increased by 74% from 2016. In 2017, the case reached 348,446. This number increased significantly compared to the previous year. A total of 335,062 cases were obtained from the Religious Courts and 13,384 cases from the National Commission on Violence against Women partner service agency [10].

3. GENDER EQUALITY

Gender is not a gender difference but a difference in social functions and roles formed by society towards women and men which results in the division of different social roles and functions [11]. The division of social roles and functions is based on what is considered appropriate and inappropriate for women and men, which are regulated according to the values, norms, customs, and habits in society [12]. Thus, gender is not natural as it can be exchanged between one place to another, and between women and men. According to the Regulation of the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection of the Republic of Indonesia, interpreting gender is a social construction based on gender differences, which is reflected in the concept of duties, rights, functions, roles, responsibilities, attitudes and behaviors given by society or culture to men and women in both public and private life [13].

The Regulation of the Ministry of Education explains that gender is a concept that refers to the different roles and responsibilities of men and women as a result of changes in the social and cultural conditions of the community [14]. It can be concluded that gender is the difference between men and women from changes in values and behavior that are socially described in the local community. In society, gender differences create gender inequality, both for men and women. This gender inequality arises when someone is treated unfairly just because of gender differences. But this gender injustice is experienced by many women so most of gender inequality problems are identified as women's problems. This is what makes men and women far from equal. Some forms of gender-based injustice (which are also known as gender injustice) cover sub-ordination (segregation), marginalization, double burden, violence, and negative labeling [15].

a. Sub-ordination (segregation)

Marginalization harms women due to limitations in terms of career development. Similarly, when working, women often get or occupy positions with lower salaries, for example as domestic workers (PRT), mass industrial factory workers (garments), or secretaries.

b. Marginalization

In this case, most women experience a double burden, for example, a wife, besides doing domestic work at home, also works to help to meet the needs. Whereas domestic work can be done by dividing the tasks with the husband. After working, most women immediately do domestic work such as taking care of children and preparing food.

c. Double burden

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d. Violence

Various forms of violence can occur at any time, such as physical, sexual, or non-sexual violence. Violence often occurs against women as women are considered weak creatures. In the household also often occurs in women as their position as a wife is considered lower than the husband so that the husband can yell, beat and commit other violence against the wife.

4. GENDER EQUALITY BECOMES A SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL (SDGS)

Currently, the Indonesian government is aggressively implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) program, which is a sustainable program that is a non-binding global agreement that is universally applicable. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) place the community at the center of development. This means that the community is the ultimate goal and as well as an active actor in development [16].

The implementation of the SDGs began with a meeting on September 25-27 2015 at the United Nations (United States of Indonesia) New York and attended by 193 countries resulting in 17 aspects of the SDGs [17]. The SDGs contain 17 goals and 169 targets that describe the goals and scope of global multidimensional inclusive development agenda consisting of 17 goals (UNDP, 2015b) [18]:

- 1) No poverty
- 2) Zero hunger
- 3) Good health and well-being
- 4) Quality education
- 5) Gender equality
- 6) Clean water and sanitation
- 7) Affordable and clean energy
- 8) Decent work and economic growth
- 9) Industry, innovation and infrastructure
- 10) Reduce inequality
- 11) Sustainable cities and communities
- 12) Responsible consumption and production
- 13) Climate action
- 14) Life below water
- 15) Life on land
- 16) Peace, justice and strong institution
- 17) Partnerships for the goal

Gender-based development is explicitly stated in the 5th goal, "Achieving Gender Equality and Empowering Women and Children". The gender equality goal as one of the SDG's goals strengthens the urgency of gender equality in human development [19]. The progress of a country will not be achieved without gender equality. Referring to Presidential Regulation No. 2 of 2015 concerning the 2015-2019 RPJMN, Presidential Decree No. 59 of 2017 was ratified on the Implementation of Sustainable Development Goal Achievement (Mada, n.d.). The 5-goals of the SDGs are affirmed in the Attachment to Presidential Decree No. 59 of 2017 [20].

The global goals of the SDGs are to achieve gender equality and empower women, and the global targets to be realized are:

- 1) End all forms of discrimination against women everywhere.
- 2) Eliminate all forms of violence against women in public and private spaces, including human trafficking and sexual exploitation, as well as various other forms of exploitation

- 3) Eliminate all harmful practices, such as child marriage, early and forced marriage, and female circumcision.
- 4) Ensure full and effective participation, and equal opportunities for women to lead at all levels of decision-making in political, economic, and community life.
- 5) Ensure universal access to sexual and reproductive health, and reproductive rights as agreed in the Program of Action of the International Conference 60 on Population and Development and the Beijing Platform as well as the reviewed documents in the conference.

From the global target of the fifth goal, namely achieving gender equality and empowering women, the National Development as outlined in the 2015-2019 RPJMN National Targets has conformity. The 2015-2019 RPJMN National Targets are as follows:

- 1) Increasing the number of gender-responsive policies supporting women's empowerment in 2019.
- 2) Decreasing the prevalence of violence cases against women and increasing comprehensive services for violence cases against women.
- 3) Increased median age at first marriage for women (maturation of age at first marriage), increased GPR/ Gross Participation Rate for SMP/SMA/MA/equivalent in 2019, increased representation of women in the DPR.
- 4) Decreased need for family planning, increased knowledge and understanding of modern contraceptive methods, and availability of regulations that guarantee women get services, information, and education related to family planning and reproductive health.

Meanwhile, in implementing the National Targets, the Government involves all agencies, both central and regional, which include: The coordinating Ministry for Human Development and Culture, Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection, Ministry of Home Affairs, Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform, Ministry of Manpower, Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs, Election Commission, State Civil Service Agency, Provincial Government, and District/City Government [21].

Although the SDGs Agenda is up to 2030, the Indonesian government has harmonized and adjusted the f National Development with the global commitments that have been mutually agreed upon related to the achievement of gender equality and women's empowerment with various instruments and efforts to make it happen [22].

Gender justice and equality can also be achieved by some means including state policies. Some State policies have been issued with the formation of laws that can guarantee the achievement of gender justice and equality, from the central to the regional levels are follows [14]:

- 1) Pancasila, the second principle of "just and civilized humanity" and the fifth principle of "social justice for all Indonesian people".
- 2) 1945 Constitution
- 3) RI Law No. 7 of 1984 about Ratification of the Convention Concerning the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women. Article 27: "every citizen has the same rights and obligations."
- 4) Presidential Instruction No. 9 of 2000 concerning Gender Mainstreaming in National Development.
- 5) Regulation of the Ministry of Home Affairs No. 132 of 2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Gender Mainstreaming in Regional Development.

5. EMPOWERMENT AS A PROGRAM AND PROCESS

Empowerment aims to make people able to do something independently without having to depend on others. The independence that exists as a result of empowerment in the form of economic independence, political independence, and others depends on the type of the existing program [23]. Empowerment is an activity allowing people to make changes in themselves through a process that can take place briefly or through a long process [12]. Empowerment can be seen in

terms of its existence as a program or as a process. Empowerment as a program is where empowerment is seen from the stages of activities in order to achieve a goal, which is usually a predetermined period [13]. The process of individual empowerment is a relatively continuous process throughout human life, obtained from the individual's experience and not a process that stops at a time (empowerment is not an end state, but a process that all human beings experience) [24]. This also applies to society, wherein in a community, the empowerment process will not end with the completion of a program, both implemented by the government and non-government institutions [6]. The empowerment process will continue as long as the community still exists and is willing to try to empower themselves. The continuous empowerment process as a cycle consists of five main stages, namely: 1) recalling empowering and non-empowering experiences, 2) Discussing discuss reasons for empowerment/empowerment), 3) Identifying a problem or project, 4) Identifying useful power bases for making changes and develop action plans and implement the 12 activities as cyclical activities.

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